

Oxidative Debenzylation and Cyclisation of 1-Aryl-or-alkyl-4-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets: Formation of S-Aryl or alkylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines or/and the Related 1,2,4-Thiadiazoles

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Depending on the nature of the solvent and the concentration of the reactants, the oxidation of 1-aryl or alkyl-4-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets is shown to afford either the 5-aryl or alkylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines or the related 1,2,4-thiadiazoles.

1, 5-Diaryl-2-S-ethyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets (I), when oxidised with bromine or iodine, have been found to undergo ring closures to *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-aryl-*S*-ethylisothiocarbamides (II) (Joshua, this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 155). On the other hand, Kurzer and Taylor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1064) have reported the formation (in 45% yield) of 5-phenylamino-3-*S*-benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole (IV) by oxidation by bromine of 1-phenyl-4-*S*-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiuret (III) in chloroform.

Since the reported yield of (IV) was not satisfactory, the reaction leading to it probably was not the only reaction taking place (Kurzer and Taylor, *loc. cit.*, p. 1066). The differing modes of ring closure observed as above could be due to the difference in the nature of the substituents in positions 1,4, and 5, or due to the change in the working conditions, or both.

In view of these facts and also in the light of the oxidation by bromine of 1,5-diphenyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiuret (V) to 5-phenylamino-3-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (VI), observed in these laboratories, a reinvestigation of the oxidations generally and interaction of bromine, especially with the above dithiobiurets, has been carried out.

The present communication describes the results obtained with 1-phenyl-, 1-*p*-tolyl-, 1-*m*-tolyl-, 1-*m*-xylyl-, 1-methyl-, 1-ethyl-, and 1-propyl²-4-*S*-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets.

Bromine in concentrated solutions in chloroform or benzene was found to afford the hydrobromides of the related 5-aryl- or -alkylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines. This reaction can be represented as:

In dilute solutions of the above reactants in the same solvents or in ethanolic solutions with bromine or iodine, another reaction (ii) took place when the principal product was 5-aryl- or -alkylamino-3-*S*-benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole (IX).

The reaction (ii) also took place to a small extent in concentrated chloroform or benzene solutions. Thus concentration of the reactants, especially the strength of the oxidant, appears to be the deciding factor whether the reaction would proceed along the route (i) or (ii).

The dithiazolidine (VIII) on reduction with alkaline sulphide easily afforded the related dithiobiuret (X).

The thiadiazoles (IX) also on similar reduction gave the dithiobiurets (X). In the case of 5-methyl-3-*S*-benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole, 1-methyl-4-*S*-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiuret was obtained as the initial reduction product; this on prolonged reduction afforded the 1-methyl-2,4-dithiobiuret which suggested the following sequence of changes (cf. Kurzer and Taylor, *loc. cit.*, p. 1067):

This was in agreement with earlier observed facts (Curd *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 740) and our own unpublished work on reductive debenylation by alkaline sulphide, that debenylation or dealkylation was not effected when there was no hydrogen on the adjoining nitrogen atoms.

In no case was a benzothiazolyl derivative obtained. The main experimental results have been summarised in Tables I to IV. In all the cases the identification of the products was carried out with authentic samples prepared by alternative methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Alkyl- or -aryl-4-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets were readily obtained by condensing the corresponding isothiocyanate with *S*-benzylisothiuronium base. Details of a typical experiment leading to the formation of 1-phenyl-4-*S*-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiuret are shown below.

S-Benzylisothiuronium chloride was mixed with an equimolecular quantity of phenylisothiocyanate and the required quantity of a 10% solution of alkali was added to neutralise the hydrochloride. The pasty mass so obtained was warmed for 10 minutes on a water bath and extracted with benzene. Benzene extract was heated under reflux for 20 to 30 minutes, solvent removed, and the residual semisolid treated with HCl (conc.) when the hydrochloride of the isodithiobiuret was obtained. It was freed of the unchanged reactants by washing with ether and cold water. The salt on basification afforded 1-phenyl-4-*S*-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiuret, crystallised from ethanol as white needles. The other 1-aryl- and -alkylisodithiobiurets were prepared similarly.

The *S*-benzylisothiuronium chloride and the isothiocyanates also condensed directly when heated on a water bath under reflux for about 2 hours, affording the corresponding isodithiobiuret hydrochlorides in good yields. Physical characteristics and the other data about the respective isodithiobiurets are recorded in Table I.

Oxidation of 1-Aryl- or 1-Alkyl-4-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets

(a) *With Bromine in Chloroform.*—The required isodithiobiuret was dissolved in minimum quantity of warm chloroform and bromine was added with good stirring. A yellowish crystalline solid separated with evolution of lachrymatory fumes of benzyl bromide. The solid was filtered, washed with ether, and dried. Crystallisation from ethanol in presence of a little hydrobromic acid afforded crystalline products. These were the hydrobromides of the related 5-substituted amino-3-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines. All the isodithiobiurets were oxidised in a similar manner. Results are summarised in Table II.

Oxidation of the isodithiobiurets in benzene and carbon tetrachloride also afforded the same products provided that the concentration of the substance in the solvent was very high and pure liquid bromine used as oxidant. With higher dilution of the solvent the dithiazolidine and the 1,2,4-thiadiazole were formed in different proportions depending on the degree of dilution of the reactants. The two products could be separated by fractional crystallisation from ethanol. The more soluble one on treatment with alkali liberated a free base which was identified as the 1,2,4-thiadiazole. The sparingly ethanol-soluble part was soluble in alkali and identified as the corresponding dithiazolidine hydrobromide (Table II).

(b) *With Bromine in Ethanol.*—To an ethanolic solution of the isodithiobiuret was added a dilute ethanolic solution of bromine till the colour of bromine persisted. The solution was stirred into excess of cold water and basified when a white solid separated. On

TABLE I
1-Aryl or alkyl-4-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets.

No. Reactants.	1-Substituted-4-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets formed.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	Hydrochloride.		Found.	Calo.
				M.P.	Equiv. wt.		
				Found.	Calo.		
1. Phenyl-I. SB.-T.C.	*1-Phenyl- (C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₃ S ₂)	Ethanol	116°	334.2 (C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	337.5	N : 13.68%	13.95%
2. <i>p</i> -Tolyl-I. SB.-T.C.	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- (C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	Methanol	120°	347.2 (C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	351.5	C : 60.65 H : 5.29 N : 13.42	60.95 5.39 13.33
3. <i>m</i> -Tolyl-I. SB.-T.C.	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- (C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	Ethanol	101°	348.3 (C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	351.5	N : 13.32	13.33
4. <i>m</i> -Xylyl-I. SB.-T.C.	1- <i>m</i> -Xylyl- (C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂)	Do	116°	359.9 (C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	365.5	N : 12.76	12.79
5. Methyl-I. SB.-T.C.	*1-Methyl- (C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	Do (75%)	97°	275.8 (C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	275.5	N : 17.30	17.57
6. Ethyl-I. SB.-T.C.	1-Ethyl- (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂)	Methanol	72°	285.3 (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	289.5	N : 16.82	16.60
7. Propyl-I. SB.-T.C.	*1-Propyl- (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	Liquid at room temp.	180°	301.6 (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	303.4		

*Kurzner and Taylor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1064).

I represents isothiocyanate.

T.C. represents isothiocuronium chloride.

SB. represents *S*-benzyl.

crystallisation from ethanol colorless, needle-shaped crystals of the related 1,2,4-thiadiazoles were obtained.

TABLE II

Oxidation of 1-aryl-or-alkyl-4-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets by bromine.

No.	Isodithiobiuret oxidised.	Solvent.	1,2,4-Dithiazolidine formed.	Yield.	M.P.	**Authentic sample m. p.	Mixed m. p.
1.	1-Phenyl-4-SB- (C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	Chloroform	5-Phenylamino-3-imino- (C ₈ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂ ,HBr)	90%	210°	210°	210°
2.	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-4-SB- (C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	„	5- <i>p</i> -Tolylamino-3-imino- (C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂ ,HBr)	90	222°	220°	221°
3.	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-4-SB- (C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	„	5- <i>m</i> -Tolylamino-3-imino- (C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂ ,HBr)*	80	205°	205°	205°
4.	1- <i>m</i> -Xylyl-4-SB- (C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂)	Benzene	5- <i>m</i> -Xylylamino-3-imino- (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂ ,HBr)*	80-85	165°	163°	165°
5.	1-Methyl-4-SB- (C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	„	5-Methylamino-3-imino- (C ₃ H ₅ N ₃ S ₂ ,HBr)*	80	225°	228°	226°
6.	1-Ethyl-4-SB- (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂)	„	5-Ethylamino-3-imino- (C ₄ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂ ,HBr)	80-85	152°	154°	154°
7.	1-Propyl-4-SB- (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	CCl ₄	5-Propyl amino-3-imino- (C ₅ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂ ,HBr)*	80	160°	162°	162°

*In these cases the related thiadiazoles were obtained in small quantities (about 10% yield).

**The hydrobromides of the dithiazolidines were obtained by oxidation of authentic dithiobiuret samples (Fromm *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1893, 1893, 275, 34; Dixit, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 44).

(c) *With Iodine in Ethanol.*—To a clear solution of the isodithiobiuret in ethanol was added an ethanolic solution of iodine till no further decolorisation took place. Treatment of the solution with an excess of water precipitated a solid product. It was collected and crystallised from ethanol. In every case the product was identical with the related 1,2,4-thiadiazole (*vide supra*). The results of these oxidations are presented in Table III.

The oxidation products obtained by the procedure (a) were identified as the hydrobromides of 5-aryl-or-alkylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines. These were also obtained by oxidation of the corresponding dithiobiurets, which were prepared by the action of amines on isopersulphocyanic acid (Fromm *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1893, 275, 34; 1908, 361, 319; Dixit, *this Journal*, 1960, 38, 44).

Reduction of 1-Alkyl-or-arylamino-3-S-benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazoles with Ammoniacal Hydrogen Sulphide.—The thiadiazoles on shaking with a solution of ammonium hydrogen sulphide in ethanol went into solution and the related dithiobiurets were thrown out after

standing for about an hour or on acidification. The product was collected and crystallised from ethanol. In some cases the reduction took place only after passing hydrogen sulphide through warm ammoniacal solution for about an hour. In the case of 5-methylamino-3-*S*-benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole, the related 1-methyl-4-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiuret was obtained as the initial reduction product, which on further reduction afforded the dithiobiuret. The dithiobiurets were identified by comparison with authentic samples prepared by the reaction of isopresulphocyanic acid and the amines (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE III

Oxidation of isodithiobiurets by bromine or iodine in ethanol.

No.	4- <i>S</i> -Benzyliso-2, 4-dithiobiurets oxidised.	3- <i>S</i> -Benzyliso-1,2,4-thiadiazole formed.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.
1.	1-Phenyl-	5-Phenylamino* (C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	Ethanol	154°	N : 14.1%	14.04%
2.	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-	5- <i>p</i> -Tolylamino- (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	„	173°	C : 61.66 H : 4.84 N : 13.39	61.34 4.79 13.41
3.	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-	5- <i>m</i> -Tolylamino- (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	Methanol	86°	N : 13.23	13.41
4.	1- <i>m</i> -Xylyl-	5- <i>m</i> -Xylylamino- (C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	Ethanol	163°	N : 12.63	12.84
5.	1-Methyl-	5-Methylamino* (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂)	Methanol	137°	C : 50.45 H : 4.46 N : 17.96	50.63 4.46 17.72
6.	1-Ethyl-	5-Ethylamino- (C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	„	67°	N : 16.60	16.73
7.	1-Propyl ^a -	5-Propyl ^a amino* (C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	„	92°	N : 15.96	15.84

*Kurzer and Taylor, *loc. cit.*.

Reduction of 5-Alkyl- or -arylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine Hydrobromides with Ammonium Hydrogen Sulphide.—The 5-alkyl- or -arylamino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines obtained in the oxidation of 1-aryl- or -alkyl-4-*S*-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets (Table II) were dissolved in ethanolic ammonium hydrogen sulphide and hydrogen sulphide passed for 10 to 15 minutes. The reaction mixture after acidification was filtered. The residue on crystallisation from ethanol or water afforded crystals of the corresponding dithiobiurets; identified by undepressed mixed melting points with authentic samples. The results are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Reduction of the oxidation products of the isodithiobiurets.

No.	Oxidation products reduced,	Dithiobiurets. formed.	Cryst from.	M.P.	Authentic sample m.p.	Mixed m.p.
1.	(a) 5-Phenylamino-T	1-Phenyl-	Ethanol	184°	**179°	182°
	(b) 4- " DA	"	"	178°	179°	179°
2.	(a) 5- <i>p</i> -Tolylamino-T	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-	"	173°	**173°	173°
	(b) 5- <i>p</i> - " DA	"	"	171°	173°	172°
3.	(a) 5- <i>m</i> -Tolylamino-T	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-	Methanol	158°	158°	158°
	(b) 5- <i>m</i> - " DA	"	"	156°	158°	158°
4.	(a) 5- <i>m</i> -Xylylamino-T	1- <i>m</i> -Xylyl-	Ethanol	120°	121°	121°
	(b) 5- <i>m</i> - " DA	"	"	120°	121°	121°
5.	(a) 5-Methylamino-T	1-Methyl-	Water	153°	*153°	153°
	(b) 5- " DA	"	"	152°	153°	153°
6.	(a) 5-Ethylamino-T	1-Ethyl-	"	175°	*176°	176°
	(b) 5- " DA	"	"	175°	176°	176°
7.	(a) 5-Propyl amino-T	1-Propyl	Ethanol (25%)	120°	*121°	121°
	(b) 5- " DA	"	"	121°	121°	121°

**Fromm *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1893, 275, 34; 1908, 361, 319.

*Dixit, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 44.

T represents 3-*S*-benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole.

DA represents 3-iminodithiazolidine.

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